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Development and implementation of data sharing policies

Collaboration of social science data archives and journals

Marijana Glavica¹, Irena Kranjec¹, Janez Štebe², Sonja Bezjak²

¹Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb, Croatian Social Science Data Archive

²Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, Social Science Data Archives

Who are we?

- Social Science Data Archives
 - **ADP**
Social Science Data Archives, Slovenia
 - **CROSSDA**
Croatian Social Science Data Archive
- providing national infrastructure public services
- **CESSDA ERIC** Service Providers

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What are we going to show you and in which context?

- Services offered by social science data archives relevant to journals' data sharing policies
- Examples of collaboration between data archives and journal editors

Context:

- Open Science, transparency, data sharing
- Slovenia and Croatia: Underdeveloped data sharing culture; Slow implementation of open data strategy by the national research funder

The TOP Guidelines were created by journals, funders, and societies to align scientific ideals with practices.

TOP provides a suite of tools to guide implementation of better, more transparent research.

[TOP](#) [Summary Table](#) [Implementing TOP](#) [Current Signatories](#) [Coordinating Committee](#)

	Not Implemented	Level I	Level II	Level III
Citation Standards	No mention of data citation.	Journal describes citation of data in guidelines to authors with clear rules and examples.	Article provides appropriate citation for data and materials used consistent with journal's author guidelines.	Article is not published until providing appropriate citation for data and materials following journal's author guidelines.
Data Transparency	Journal encourages data sharing, or says nothing.	Article states whether data are available, and, if so, where to access them.	Data must be posted to a trusted repository. Exceptions must be identified at article submission.	Data must be posted to a trusted repository, and reported analyses will be reproduced independently prior to publication.
Analytic Methods (Code) Transparency	Journal encourages code sharing, or says nothing.	Article states whether code is available, and, if so, where to access it.	Code must be posted to a trusted repository. Exceptions must be identified at article submission.	Code must be posted to a trusted repository, and reported analyses will be reproduced independently prior to publication.
Research	Journal	Article states	Materials must be	Materials must be

Services

- Long-term curated data collections
- Quality control (data consistency, anonymisation checks, documentation completeness)
- Personalised expert curation support for data and metadata preparation and deposit
- PIDs and versioning
- Links to publications
- Standard licences
- Training, advice and active support for data management planning
- Promotion of data usage

Slovenian case

- Implementing the [RDA Research Data Policy Framework](#) in Slovenian scientific journals
- Partners from other RIs: [ELIXIR-SI](#), [CLARIN-SI](#), [DARIAH-SI](#)
- Journals participating in a pilot from different fields: archaeology, history, linguistics and social sciences
- Continued cooperation with ADP: Until now, four social science journals have implemented research data policies:
 - [Socialno delo Journal](#)
 - [Central European Public Administration Review](#)
 - [Economic and Business Review](#)
 - [Social Science Forum](#) [Družboslovne razprave]

CESSDA Journals Outreach

- Dialogs with journal editors - what are their views on data sharing?
- Discussing possibilities of support that can be provided for journals by data archives
- Exploring capacities of data archives for supporting journals
- Connecting data archives; developing services related to journals' data sharing policies
- Organising events
 - [Open forum: Challenges of sharing data linked to publications](#)
 - Making Social Science Transparent
 - [Journal and Data Archive Collaboration Forum](#) **UPCOMING!**
Nov 8, 2022 @14:00-16:30

PARTNERS

- GESIS, Germany
- CROSSDA, Croatia
- EKKE, Greece
- ADP, Slovenia
- FORS, Switzerland
- FSD, Finland
- SND, Sweden
- TARKI, Hungary
- DCS, Serbia

Croatian case

- Started a dialog with 3 editors of Croatian social science journals
- [Croatian Sociological Review](#) introduced its first open science policy in 2021
- Considering various epistemological assumptions in the humanities and social sciences
- The next step: in cooperation with CROSSDA, define instructions for authors and reviewers to make this policy official
- 2022 Webinar co-organised with the CROASC: [The role of journals in encouraging access to research data](#)

CROSSDA

CROASC
Croatian Association
for Scholarly
Communication

Vučković Juroš, T. (2021). Looking Ahead: Fast-Track Research Notes and Open Science Policy. *Revija za sociologiju*, 51(3), 301-307. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/269681>

Vlašiček, D. & Flis, I. (2021). Otvorena znanost. Kratak pregled pokreta i metodološkog značaja. *Revija za sociologiju*, 51(3), 507-516. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/269814>

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Thank you.